

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIPOSITIVE SILVER WITH PYRIDINE CARBOXYLIC ACIDS. PART II. ARGENTIC COMPOUNDS OF PYRIDINE DICARBOXYLIC ACIDS

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In continuation of our previous work on bivalent silver complexes of pyridine monocarboxylic acids, we have now been able to prepare the argentic complexes of all the dicarboxylic acids of pyridine with the exception of that of dinicotinic acid, which is not at hand for the present.

Argentiferous complexes of quinolinic, cinchomeronic, isocinchomeronic, lutidinic and dipicolinic acids are formed by the oxidation of silver nitrate in presence of the corresponding acid by alkali persulphate in aqueous medium. They form red to dark red, finely divided crystals, more or less sparingly soluble in water. The argentic complex of dipicolinic acid has, however, been obtained in two different colours - dark red and green, the last one being produced at a lower temperature. The composition of all these complexes is given by the general formula $Ag_2(XH)_2$ (where XH_2 = one molecule of the pyridine dicarboxylic acid). With the exception of cinchomeronic acid (3 : 4), all the complexes may be represented by a monomeric structure like that of the argentic picolinate. The structure of the argentic cinchomerionate resembles possibly that of nicotinic or isonicotinic acid, being either dimeric, or polymeric with the formation of unending two-dimensional sheets and layers. The complexes are all decomposed by acids and alkalis.

All these argentic complexes are paramagnetic and give moment values of approximately $1.73 \mu_B$. X-ray powder photographs show that the green and chocolate modifications of the argentic complex of dipicolinic acid differ in their crystal structure. Capric and argentic quinolinates crystallise with different water molecules and hence show, as might be expected, different X-ray patterns.

In a previous paper (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 503) an account of the preparation properties and constitution of the argentic complexes of pyridine monocarboxylic acids, like nicotinic and isonicotinic acids, has been given, which, with the argentic picolinate previously described by Barbieri (*Atti Accad. Lincei*, 1933, 17, 1078), show that all the three pyridine monocarboxylic acids (α , β and γ) are capable of forming chelate inner-metallic complexes with bivalent silver. It has now been observed that pyridine dicarboxylic acids also behave in a similar manner. Of the six different pyridine dicarboxylic acids, argentic complexes with five of these, viz., quinolinic (2 : 3), cinchomeronic (3 : 4), isocinchomeronic (2 : 5), lutidinic (2 : 4) and dipicolinic (2 : 6) acids, have been prepared for the present. It has, however, not yet been possible to obtain the remaining 3 : 5-dicarboxylic acid of pyridine (diniticotinic acid) in sufficient quantities to investigate the formation of its argentic complex.

The argentic complexes of all the above pyridine dicarboxylic acids are formed by the oxidation of silver nitrate in the presence of the acid concerned by means of sodium or potassium persulphate in aqueous medium in the cold. All the complexes excepting that of 2 : 6-acid (dipicolinic acid) form red to dark red crystalline products; while the latter gives rise to two different coloured forms, green and dark chocolate. Their composition is represented by the general formula, $Ag_2(XH)_2$ (where XH_2 = one molecule of the dicarboxylic acid). One of the $-COOH$ groups of each ligand molecule

remains obviously free in the complex. All the complexes, with the exception of that of cinchomeronic acid (3:4), are possibly represented by a monomeric structure like that of argentic picolinate. The structure of the argentic complex of cinchomeronic acid is presumably related to that of nicotinic or isonicotinic acid, being either dimeric, or polymeric with the formation of unending two-dimensional sheets or layers. (cf. Banerjee and Rây, *loc. cit.*). All the argentic complexes, as expected, are paramagnetic with a moment value of approximately $1.73 \mu_B$.

Dübsky and Okác (*Coll. Czech. Chem. Com.*, 1931, 3, 465), Lukes and Jurecek (*ibid.*, 1948, 13, 131), as well as others have described Cu^{II} salts of many of these pyridine dicarboxylic acids. They have, however, found that in most cases the composition of the copper compound is given by one atom of copper combining with one of the acid molecule. But in the case of lutidinic (2:4), quinolinic (2:3) and dipicolinic (2:6) acids, copper compounds with two molecules of the acid per atom of copper have also been described. The compositions of these latter differ from their corresponding argentic compounds, as described here, in their water of hydration, which presumably accounts for their different X-ray pictures obtained for the compounds of quinolinic acid (2:3). Burada (*An. Sci. Univ. Jassy*, 1935, 20, 71) described a silver^{II} quinolate with one molecule of water, resembling the corresponding copper compound. We have, however, failed to verify this, as the silver complex prepared by us has always been found to contain two molecules of water of hydration.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the complex argentic compounds of pyridine dicarboxylic acids were prepared by adding the finely powdered acid to the solution of sodium or potassium persulphate almost simultaneously with silver nitrate solution, while the mixture was constantly stirred by means of a magnetic stirrer. The stirring was continued for about 3 hours for complete oxidation. It should, however, be noted that silver nitrate and the acid should not be allowed to come together in the absence of persulphate, as in that case highly insoluble univalent silver salt of the pyridine carboxylic acid is formed, which it is very difficult to oxidise.

1. *Argentic Quinolate*.—It was obtained by Burada (*loc. cit.*) by oxidising silver quinoline nitrate, $\text{A}_2(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N})_2\text{NO}_2$, with an excess of ammonium persulphate in aqueous solution. The composition of his compound is given by $\text{Ag}^{II}(\text{XH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

In the present case, quinolinic acid was prepared by the oxidation of quinoline with alkaline potassium permanganate solution on the water-bath (Koenigs, *Ber.*, 1879, 12, 983). For the preparation of the argentic quinolate, quinolinic acid (0.6 g.) in a finely divided state was added to sodium persulphate (3 g.), dissolved in the minimum quantity of cold water, followed immediately by a solution of silver nitrate (0.3 g.) in a little water. The mixture was stirred continuously for 3 hours. The colour of the mixture gradually turned orange-red. When no further change had occurred, the product was filtered through sintered glass-bed filter, washed with cold water till free of sulphate, and then dried in a vacuum desiccator, placed in a refrigerator. Yield 0.7-0.8 g.

The orange-red crystalline product is very sparingly soluble in water. It is quite stable in dry air in the cold and remains unchanged even after 3 months. The substance is readily decomposed by acids and alkalis; it liberates iodine from acid solutions of potassium iodide. [Found: Ag(oxidimetric), 22.41; Ag(gravimetric), 22.83; C, 35.81. $\text{Ag}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{NO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ag, 22.69; C, 35.30%]. The substance was found to be paramagnetic. $\chi_m = 2.236 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m(\text{corr.}) = 1247 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_n = 1.743$.

2. *Argentio Cinchomerate*.—Cinchomeric acid was prepared by the oxidation of quinine in a boiling mixture of concentrated and fuming nitric acid for about 150 hours (Kass, *Monatsh.*, 1902, **23**, 252).

The argentic complex was prepared exactly in the same way as the argentic quinolate described above, yield 0.8 g. The substance forms dark red crystals and is quite stable in the dry air for months. It behaves like the previous compound. It does not decompose even when heated to 70° for one hour and is unaffected by light. [Found: Ag(oxidimetric), 24.41; Ag(gravimetric), 24.70; C, 38.98. $\text{Ag}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{NO}_4)_2$ requires Ag, 24.54; C, 38.18%]. $\chi_m = 2.434 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m(\text{corr.}) = 1232 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_n = 1.742$.

3. *Argentio isocinchomerate*.—*isocinchomeric* and *lutidinic* acids were prepared by the oxidation of a mixture of 2:5- and 2:4-dimethylpyridine (commercially available) with potassium permanganate solution on a water-bath with mechanical stirring (cf. Garkow, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 2063; Ladenburg, *Ber.*, 1885, **18**, 915). The dimethylpyridine mixture (10 g.) was oxidised with KMnO_4 (72 g.) in aqueous solution. After complete oxidation, when the colour of the permanganate disappeared, the mixture was filtered from the precipitated oxides of manganese. The clear colorless filtrate was cooled to 10° and acidified with HCl (indicated by Congo-red), when a heavy white precipitate of the mixture of 2:4- and 2:5-pyridine dicarboxylic acids separated out. These were then separated from each other by repeated extraction with hot water. The 2:4-acid (*lutidinic* acid), soluble in hot water, was freed from the admixture of 2:5-acid (*isocinchomeric* acid), the latter is difficultly soluble even in boiling water. The purity of the products was verified by determination of their melting points.

For the preparation of argentic complex of *isocinchomeric* acid, 0.413 g. of the acid was employed for 0.3 g. of AgNO_3 and 3 g. of sodium persulphate; yield 0.6 g. The preparation was carried out at 30° and the stirring was continued for about 5 hours. As the acid is highly insoluble, any excess should be carefully avoided.

The substance forms brick-red powder, insoluble in water; it is quite stable in air and remains unchanged for months. Its properties are similar to those of the previous compounds. [Found: Ag (oxidimetric), 24.21; Ag (gravimetric), 24.36; C 38.12. $\text{Ag}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{NO}_4)_2$ requires Ag, 24.54; C, 38.18%]. $\chi_m = 2.346 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m(\text{corr.}) = 1194 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_n = 1.712$.

4. *Argentio Lutidinate*.—The complex argentic compound of *lutidinic* acid (2:4) was prepared like the previous compound, using the same quantity of materials. The colour and other properties are closely allied to those of argentic *isocinchomerate*.

[Found: Ag (oxidimetric), 24.18; Ag (gravimetric), 24.66; C, 38.08. $\text{Ag}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{NO}_4)_2$ requires Ag, 24.54; C, 38.18%]. $\chi_m = 2.113 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m(\text{corr.}) = 1091 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_n = 1.644$.

5. *Argentio Dipicolinate*.—(a) *Green*. This was prepared like the previous compound, but the reaction temperature was maintained near about 15° . The mixture turned dark green with the separation of fine green crystals. Yield is almost the same as that of the argentic quinolinate.

The substance is moderately soluble in water, giving a green solution. In the solid state it is rather unstable except in the cold and dry state. When kept at the room temperature it gradually turns dark grey. [Found: Ag (oxidimetric), 21.15; Ag (gravimetric), 20.99; C, 33.02. $\text{Ag}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{NO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ag, 21.09; C, 33.81%]. $\chi_m = 2.2 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m(\text{corr.}) = 1252 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_n = 1.747$.

(b) *Chocolate*.—The preparation of this variety is similar to that of the green form, with this difference that the temperature is maintained at about 25° . From the green solution the product separated as a dark chocolate crystalline powder.

The substance, however, dissolves in water forming a green solution. It is somewhat more stable than the green form. In all other respects they behave alike. [Found: Ag (oxidimetric), 22.55; Ag (gravimetric), 22.83; C, 36.20; H, 2.65. $\text{Ag}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{NO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ag, 22.69; C, 35.30; H, 2.52%]. $\chi_m = 2.441 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m(\text{corr.}) = 1345 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_n = 1.807$.

The difference in colour of these two modifications is possibly caused by their difference in hydration, and the consequent difference in their crystal structure as revealed by their X-ray powder photographs (*vide infra*). There is no evidence, however, to prove that they might be related as *cis-trans* isomers of one and the same compound.

TABLE I

Argentio quinolinate, $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fig. 1).

θ .	d .	Intensity.	θ .	d .	Intensity.	θ .	d .	Intensity.
$4^\circ 42$	9.4004	80	$14^\circ 8$	3.1546	2	$21^\circ 26$	2.1064	5
$6^\circ 28$	7.0192	25	$14^\circ 52$	3.0021	5	$21^\circ 43$	2.0817	7
$7^\circ 20$	6.0354	40	$15^\circ 11$	2.9222	7	$22^\circ 14$	2.0356	25
$8^\circ 5$	5.4780	85	$16^\circ 7$	2.7749	25	$23^\circ 3$	1.9673	5
$9^\circ 3$	4.8968	1	$16^\circ 52$	2.6547	85	$24^\circ 30$	1.8574	20
$9^\circ 49$	4.5178	30	$17^\circ 25$	2.5735	2	$25^\circ 54$	1.7634	15
$10^\circ 27$	4.2458	10	$18^\circ 12$	2.4661	5	$26^\circ 21$	1.7354	2
$11^\circ 30$	3.8635	100	$18^\circ 54$	2.3779	7	$26^\circ 59$	1.6971	2
$12^\circ 15$	3.6302	25	$19^\circ 56$	2.2529	25	$27^\circ 24$	1.6737	1
$12^\circ 21$	3.6013	5	$20^\circ 1$	2.2502	5	$27^\circ 52$	1.6479	1
$13^\circ 45$	3.2407	1	$26^\circ 30$	2.1994	25	$28^\circ 22$	1.6213	

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

TABLE II
Copper quinolate, H₂O (Fig. 2).

θ .	d .	Intensity.	θ .	d .	Intensity.	θ .	d .	Intensity.
5°52	7.5362	95	15°21	2.9098	25	21°49	2.0726	25
6°18	7.0192	95	16°21	2.7363	10	22°48	1.9877	7
6°31	6.7871	15	16°58	2.6396	5	23°12	1.9552	2
6°55	6.3963	20	17°24	2.5758	10	24°16	1.8741	2
11°21	3.9197	100	17°56	2.5016	10	24°45	1.8398	5
11°58	3.7154	15	18°25	2.4381	5	25°12	1.8091	5
12°52	3.4591	35	19°25	2.3170	15	25°58	1.7592	7
13°15	3.3507	5	19°58	2.2557	1	27°10	1.6871	20
14°1	3.1803	7	20°6	2.2412	10	28°3	1.6380	12
14°58	2.9825	2	21°10	2.1332	5	29°9	1.5813	18

TABLE III
Argentio dipicolinate, 4H₂O (green) (Fig. 3).

θ .	d .	Intensity.	θ .	d .	Intensity.	θ .	d .	Intensity.
4°21	10.1570	90	11°53	3.7406	2	20°36	2.1892	10
6°9	7.1903	95	12°17	3.6204	1	22°3	2.0518	1
7°12	6.1456	15	13°23	3.3277	100	22°39	2.0002	1
8°7	5.4556	1	14°29	3.0798	5	23°10	1.9578	10
9°5	4.8789	25	15°25	2.8975	1	24°37	1.8492	3
10°19	4.3011	25	16°28	2.7173	7	25°13	1.8080	1
11°18	3.9310	20	17°59	2.4948	10	26°10	1.7466	10
			19°25	2.3170	10			

TABLE IV
Argentio dipicolinate, 2H₂O (chocolate) (Fig. 4).

θ .	d .	Intensity.	θ .	d .	Intensity.	θ .	d .	Intensity.
4°18	10.273	85	11°48	3.7666	95	20°9	2.2359	40
5°36	7.8933	95	12°41	3.5081	1	21°35	2.0939	40
6°4	7.2886	1	13°36	3.2757	95	22°33	2.0086	5
7°33	5.8615	60	14°44	3.0287	2	23°19	1.9460	15
8°9	5.4335	60	15°27	2.8914	1	23°54	1.8612	5
9°1	4.9147	1	16°22	2.7335	1	24°51	1.8329	50
9°44	4.5561	100	17°8	2.6147	40	25°31	1.7881	3
10°41	4.1486	30	18°6	2.4793	40	26°9	1.7477	30
			18°48	2.3901	10			

X-ray measurements.—X-ray powder photographs of argentic quinolate, $\text{Ag}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{NO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and of the corresponding copper compound, $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{NO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, as well as of the green and chocolate modifications of argentic dipicolinate were taken in a cylindrical 9 cm Unicam camera with Cu.K_α -radiation from Raymax demountable rotating anode tube at a voltage of 30 kV with a tube current of 50 mA. The time of exposure in each case was 3 hours.

It is evident from the measurement given above that cupric quinolate and argentic quinolate differ in their crystalline structure, as might be expected from the difference in their water of hydration. The two differently coloured modifications of argentic dipicolinate also show different structures, as already stated.

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